

A RATE DEPENDENT ANISOTROPIC DAMAGE MODEL FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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SUMMARY: A coupled incremental damage and plasticity theory for rate independent and rate dependent composite materials is introduced here. This allows damage to be path dependent either on the stress history or thermodynamic force conjugate to damage. This is achieved through the use of an incremental damage tensor. Damage and inelastic deformations are incorporated in the proposed model that is used for the analysis of fiber-reinforced metal matrix composite materials. The damage is described kinematically in both the elastic and inelastic domains using the fourth order damage effect tensor which is a function of the second-order damage tensor. A physical interpretation of the second order damage tensor is given in this work which relates to the microcrack porosity within the unit cell.

A three step split operator algorithm is used in this work to additively decompose the set of differential equations into the elastic, plastic and damage deformation. In order to test the validity of the model, a series of uniaxial test experiments are conducted for damage characterization of the metal matrix composite. The experiments and numerical simulations are conducted for laminate layups $(90)_{8s}$ and are tested under uniaxial tension.

KEYWORDS Composites, Anisotropy, Damage, Rate Effects, Elevated Temperatures

INTRODUCTION

The coupling of damage and inelastic deformation in materials have been studied only recently [6,5,13]. Both Ju [6] and Johansson [5] made use of the effective stress utilizing a scalar measure of isotropic damage. Voyiadjis and Park [13] made use of the effective configuration by invoking the kinematics of damage through the use of a second order damage tensor. Voyiadjis and Park [12] reviewed a linear transformation tensor, defined as a fourth order damage effect tensor and focused on its geometric symmetrization method in order to describe the kinematics of damage using the second order damage tensor. They utilized the polar decomposition [13] of the deformation gradient and introduced the kinematics of damage using the damage effect tensor

which does not only symmetrize the effective stress tensor but can also be related to the deformation gradient of damage. Using the consistent thermodynamic formulation one introduces separately the strain due to damage and the associated dissipation energy of this strain [13].

For the numerical simulation of boundary value problems involving damage Simo and Ju [11] assumed an additive split of the stress tensor. Ju [6] in his work assumed an additive split of the strain tensor into the elastic-damage and plastic-damage parts from the outset. This is more appealing since it is analogous to the J integral in nonlinear fracture mechanics [6]. It also results in more robust tangent moduli than the "stress-split" formulation. In the present work a three step split operator algorithm is used in order to additively decompose the set of differential equations into the elastic, inelastic, and damage deformations. This is accomplished by making use of the effective undamaged configuration of the material [12,13]. The elastic and inelastic deformations are additively split through the strain tensor in the effective undamaged configuration of the material. Although, Ju [6] also used the effective configuration in his numerical analysis, however, this was only applied to the stress tensor. This is because the kinematics of damage is not introduced in this work but is accounted indirectly through the reduction in stiffness. Ju [6] emphasizes that "added flexibility" due to the existence of microcrack is already embedded in the deformation gradient implicitly.

RATE DEPENDENT DAMAGE COUPLED WITH RATE DEPENDENT PLACTICITY

In order to account for both loading rate dependency and regularizing the localization problems a viscous anisotropic damage mechanism needs to be implemented. Such a model accounts for retardation of the micro-crack growth at higher strain rates. The proposed rate dependent damage model is based on the mathematical formulation of the overstress type modeling of rate dependent plasticity. For rate dependent damage an overstress conjugate force type damage function is postulated. The coupled equation between the rate dependent plastic strain rate and damage rate is given as follows

$$\dot{\epsilon}^{vp} = \|\dot{\epsilon}^{vp}\| \mathbf{n}^{vp} + \|\dot{\phi}\| \mathbf{n}^{vpd} \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\phi} = \|\dot{\epsilon}^{vp}\| \mathbf{n}^{dvp} + \|\dot{\phi}\| \mathbf{n}^d \quad (2)$$

In equations (1) and (2) $\|\dot{\epsilon}^{vp}\|$ and $\|\dot{\phi}\|$ are the magnitudes of the plastic strain rate and damage rate which can be decomposed into a product of two functions respectively [4] using the Zener parameters such that

$$\|\dot{\epsilon}^{vp}\| = \vartheta^{vp}(T) Z^{vp} \geq 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$\|\dot{\phi}\| = \vartheta^d(T) Z^d \geq 0 \quad (3b)$$

The unit tensors \mathbf{n}^{vp} , \mathbf{n}^{vpd} , \mathbf{n}^{dvp} and \mathbf{n}^d are used to identify the direction of flow of the plastic strain and damage and are expressed as follows, respectively

$$\mathbf{n}^{vp} = \frac{\frac{\partial F^{vp}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}}{\left\| \frac{\partial F^{vp}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right\|}, \quad \mathbf{n}^{vpd} = \frac{\frac{\partial G^d}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}}{\left\| \frac{\partial G^d}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right\|} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{n}^{dvp} = \frac{\frac{\partial F^{vp}}{\partial \mathbf{Y}}}{\left\| \frac{\partial F^{vp}}{\partial \mathbf{Y}} \right\|}, \quad \mathbf{n}^d = \frac{\frac{\partial G^d}{\partial \mathbf{Y}}}{\left\| \frac{\partial G^d}{\partial \mathbf{Y}} \right\|} \quad (5)$$

where F^{vp} and G^d are the dynamic potentials for viscoplasticity and damage and their expressions are given respectively as follows

$$F^{vp} = \left\{ \frac{f^*}{[R(r) + \sigma_y(\dot{\epsilon}_o)]} + 1 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \quad (6)$$

$$G^d = \left\{ \frac{g^*}{[K(\kappa) + \sigma_d(\dot{\epsilon}_o)]} + 1 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \quad (7)$$

where f^* and g^* represent the equilibrium surfaces of viscoplasticity and damage and are strain rate dependent. The equilibrium surfaces are given as follows

$$f^* = \left(\frac{3}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^* - \mathbf{X}) : (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^* - \mathbf{X}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - [R(p) + \sigma_y(\dot{\epsilon})] \leq 0 \quad (8)$$

$$g^* = (Y_{ij}^* - ,_{ij})P_{ijkl}(Y_{kl}^* - ,_{kl}) - 1 = 0 \quad (9)$$

The functional dependency of the initial threshold values of plasticity and damage on the strain rate, is obtained through the function $Q(z)$ [10] such that

$$\sigma_y(z) = A \tanh z$$

$$z = C \ln \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} B_{abcd} \dot{\epsilon}_{ab} \dot{\epsilon}_{cd} \right]$$

where A , \mathbf{B} , and C are appropriate material parameters. $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^*$ and \mathbf{Y}^* are the stresses and conjugate forces respectively on the equilibrium surfaces. It is postulated that $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^*$ lies on the line joining the current state of stress and the

center of the equilibrium surface [14]. The same applies for the conjugate equilibrium force. The equilibrium stresses can be written as follows

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^* = \mathbf{X} + c^{vp}(\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{X}) \quad (10)$$

A similar expression is obtained for the conjugate equilibrium force

$$\mathbf{Y}^* = \boldsymbol{\Gamma} + c^d(\mathbf{Y} - \boldsymbol{\Gamma}) \quad (11)$$

c^{vp} and c^d can be obtained by using equations (10) and (11) in equations (8) and (9) respectively and the corresponding expressions are given below

$$c^{vp} = \sqrt{\frac{[R(p) + \sigma_y(z)]}{\frac{3}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{X}) : (\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{X})}} \quad (12)$$

$$c^d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(Y_{ij} - ,_{ij})P_{ijkl}(Y_{kl} - ,_{kl})}} \quad (13)$$

The final form of the viscoplastic strain rate and damage rate can be rewritten in the uncoupled form as follows

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^{vp} = \left(\frac{\langle \|\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{X}\| - \sigma_y^{*vp} \rangle}{D^{vp}} \right)^{n_1} \mathbf{n}^{vp} = \frac{F^{n_1}}{\eta^{vp}} \mathbf{n}^{vp} \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{\phi} = \left(\frac{\langle \|\mathbf{Y} - \boldsymbol{\Gamma}\| - Y^{*d} \rangle}{D^d} \right)^{n_2} \mathbf{n}^d = \frac{G^{n_2}}{\eta^d} \mathbf{n}^d \quad (15)$$

The terms, σ^{vp} and Y^d , are the overstress of viscoplasticity and damage respectively. σ_y^{*vp} is defined as $\sigma_y^{*vp} = [R(r) + \sigma_y(\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}})]$. Similarly $Y^{*d} = [K(\kappa) + Y_d(\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}})]$. The terms, D^{vp} and D^d are the drag forces which represent the isotropic hardening effects. η^{vp} and η^d are defined as $(\frac{1}{D^{vp}})^{n_1}$ and $(\frac{1}{D^d})^{n_2}$ respectively and " n_1 ", and " n_2 " are the exponents for the potential functions of viscoplasticity and damage respectively. Superscripts imply exponents only in the case of the bracketed terms.

A Physical Interpretation of the Damage Tensor

Damage in this work is characterized as the net area decrease due to a three-dimensional distribution of micro-cracks or micro-voids [9]. A differential tetrahedron is considered at point "O" in an undamaged continuum in the initial configuration, C_o , as indicated in Figure 1(a) [2]. An element PQR of an arbitrary orientation is shown in Figure 1(b) for the deformed damaged material in the current configuration C . The line elements OP, OQ, OR and area

Figure 1: Polar Decomposition of the Deformation Gradient Incorporating Damage

PQR in the current configuration, C , are represented respectively by the differential lengths dx_1, dx_2, dx_3 and the vector $d\mathbf{S}$ in the three-dimensional vector space where the x_i axes coincide with the principal damage axes. Figure 1(a) shows the corresponding differential lengths dx_1^o, dx_2^o, dx_3^o and the vector $d\mathbf{S}^o$ in the initial undamaged configuration, C_o . The deformation gradient from C_o to C is represented by \mathbf{F} . A fictitious effective undamaged configuration, \bar{C} , is postulated as shown in Figure 1(c) with an area reduction due to the damage brought about by the micro-cracks and the micro-cavities. The deformation gradient from C to \bar{C} is represented by \mathbf{F}^d . The direction of vectors $d\mathbf{S}$ and $d\bar{\mathbf{S}}$ are not necessarily coincident since the reduction due to damage is not only confined in the PQR plane but in other planes with other orientations. In Figures 1(d) and 1(e) the elastically unloaded configurations C_u and \bar{C}_u are respectively postulated. C_u represents the elastically unloaded damaged configuration with the deformation gradient from C to C_u being represented by \mathbf{F}^e . However, \bar{C}_u , represents the fictitious, effective elastically unloaded configuration with the deformation gradient from \bar{C} to \bar{C}_u being represented by $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^e$. The two deformation gradient \mathbf{F}^e and $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^e$ are not equal since \mathbf{F}^e incorporates some elastic recovered damage. This does not imply the healing of the material.

The work of Betten [2] is followed here in characterizing the anisotropic damage tensor. In three dimensional space a parallelogram formed by the

vectors \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} can be represented as follows:

$$S_i = \epsilon_{ijk} V_j W_k \quad (16)$$

or in dual form as follows

$$S_{ij} = \epsilon_{ijk} S_k \quad (17)$$

where ϵ_{ijk} is the permutation tensor. In a rectilinear three-dimensional space the absolute values of the components S_{12}, S_{23}, S_{31} are projections of the area of the parallelogram on the coordinate planes. The S_{ij} represents the area vector in a three-dimensional space and has an orientation fixed by the cross product shown in equation(16).

The deformation gradient \mathbf{F}^d is used to express the differential lengths $d\bar{x}_i$ in the effective configuration \bar{C} in terms of the differential lengths dx_i in the current deformed damaged configuration C such that

$$d\bar{x}_i = F_{ij}^d dx_j \quad (18)$$

The reduction in area between the current, C , and effective, \bar{C} , configurations may be described in terms of the eigenvalues of the second order tensor ϕ such that

$$d\bar{S}_1 = (1 - \hat{\phi}_1) dS_1, \quad d\bar{S}_2 = (1 - \hat{\phi}_2) dS_2, \quad d\bar{S}_3 = (1 - \hat{\phi}_3) dS_3 \quad (19)$$

Making use of equations (18) through (19) one obtains the eigenvalues of \mathbf{F}^d in terms of the eigenvalues of ϕ such that

$$\hat{F}_{11}^d = \sqrt{\frac{(1 - \hat{\phi}_2)(1 - \hat{\phi}_3)}{(1 - \hat{\phi}_1)}}, \quad \hat{F}_{22}^d = \sqrt{\frac{(1 - \hat{\phi}_1)(1 - \hat{\phi}_3)}{(1 - \hat{\phi}_2)}} \quad (20)$$

$$\hat{F}_{33}^d = \sqrt{\frac{(1 - \hat{\phi}_1)(1 - \hat{\phi}_2)}{(1 - \hat{\phi}_3)}} \quad (21)$$

The resulting Jacobian of the damage deformation gradient is expressed as follows

$$J^d = \hat{F}_{11}^d \hat{F}_{22}^d \hat{F}_{33}^d = \sqrt{(1 - \hat{\phi}_1)(1 - \hat{\phi}_2)(1 - \hat{\phi}_3)} \quad (22)$$

Since the fictitious effective deformed configuration denoted by \bar{C} is obtained by removing the damages from the real deformed configuration denoted by C , therefore the differential volume of the fictitious effective deformed volume denoted by $d\bar{V}$ is obtained as follows

$$d\bar{V} = \left(\sqrt{(1 - \hat{\phi}_1)(1 - \hat{\phi}_2)(1 - \hat{\phi}_3)} \right) dV \quad (23)$$

dV^d is the volume of damage in configuration C . Equation (23) may be expressed alternatively as

$$(1 - d)^2 \equiv \left(\frac{dV - dV^d}{dV} \right)^2 = (1 - \hat{\phi}_1)(1 - \hat{\phi}_2)(1 - \hat{\phi}_3) \quad (24)$$

where d is a measure of volume reduction due to the presence of micro-cavities and micro-cracks caused by damage. In the case when the volume reduction is infinitesimal (that is when $\hat{\phi}_1\hat{\phi}_2$, $\hat{\phi}_1\hat{\phi}_3$, $\hat{\phi}_2\hat{\phi}_3$, and $\hat{\phi}_1\hat{\phi}_2\hat{\phi}_3$ can be considered negligible when compared to $\hat{\phi}_i$), then equation (24) reduces to the following by ignoring higher order terms in $\hat{\phi}$

$$(1 - d^i)^2 = 1 - (\hat{\phi}_1 + \hat{\phi}_2 + \hat{\phi}_3) \quad (25)$$

Infinitesimal damage does not reflect necessarily small strain theory. In equations (24) and (25) d and d^i are measures of volume reduction due to damage. The measures d and d^i are equal to $(\frac{a^3}{dV})$ assuming only one single micro-crack where ‘ a ’ is the radius of an assumed single spherical micro-crack and dV is the volume of a representative unit cell in the mesostructure [3,7,6].

IMPLIMENTATION OF THE VISCOPLASTIC DAMAGE MODEL

The developed viscoplastic damage models are used here to numerically predict the inelastic response of composite materials. The program flow is outlined as follows

Flow of the Program

1. **Load** Increments $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \text{constant}$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{N} = \text{Applied Load Increment}$$

$$\mathbf{N}_{n+1} = \mathbf{N}_n + \Delta \mathbf{N}_n$$

2. **Newthon Raphson** Iteration $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta \epsilon]_{n+1}^{(i+1)} &= [\mathbf{A}(\dot{\epsilon})^{-1}]_{n+1}^{(i)} [\Delta \mathbf{N}]_{n+1}^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_{n+1}^{i+1} &= \epsilon_{n+1}^i + \Delta \epsilon_{n+1}^{i+1} \end{aligned}$$

3. **Loop 1** over the number of plies $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta \epsilon]_{n+1}^{(i+1,k)} &= [\mathbf{T}_k] : [\mathbf{A}^{-1}]_{n+1}^{(i)} [\Delta \mathbf{N}]_{n+1}^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_{n+1}^{(i+1,k)} &= \epsilon_{n+1}^{(i,k)} + \Delta \epsilon_{n+1}^{(i+1,k)} \end{aligned}$$

4. **Loop** over the number of the phases $r = m, f$

$$\left[\Delta \epsilon \right]_{n+1}^{(i+1,k,r)} = \left[\mathbf{A} \right]_{n+1}^{(i,k,r)} \left[\mathbf{T}_k \right] \left[\mathbf{A} \right]_{n+1}^{(i+1,k,r)} \left[\Delta \mathbf{N} \right]_{n+1}^{(i+1,k,r)}$$

5. **Split** the constitutive equation into Elastic, Viscoplastic, and Damage parts
6. **Check** the viscoplasticity condition **If** the case is viscoplastic **then** perform the viscoplastic correction algorithm
7. **Check** the damage condition **If** the case is damage **and if** the case in Step 6 is viscoplastic **then** perform the rate dependent damage correction algorithm **goto** Step 8 **else if** the case in Step 6 is elastic **then** perform only rate independent damage correction algorithm
8. **Compute** the load \mathbf{N} at the current updated stress σ_k by using the relation

$$\mathbf{N} = \int_{-h_2}^{h_1} \sigma_k dz$$

9. **Check** the condition **if** $(\mathbf{N}^{(i+1)} - \mathbf{N}^{(i)}) \leq \text{TOL}$ **then** next loading **else** goto next iteration **STEP 1**

Discussion for the Results of Viscoplastic Damage Analysis

The computational analysis of the viscoplastic damage model is performed for the laminate systems of $(90)_{8s}$ at elevated temperatures of 538°C . The viscoplastic model parameters are obtained by best fit of the the viscoplasticity model with the available experimental results [1]. This is indicated in Figure 2. The viscoplastic model parameters obtained from this analysis are then used in the viscoplastic damage analysis. In Figure 3 the viscoplastic damage model predictions for uniaxially loading of the $(90)_{8s}$ system at 538°C are compared with the experimental results and other viscoplastic models, and finite element analyses which are obtained by Majumdar and Newaz [8]. As seen clearly from the plots, the proposed model provides better predictions for the response of the material at elevated temperatures than the other models. At elevated temperatures the material becomes more ductile which may cause retardation of the damage in the material. This is because of the possibility of increase in the bond strength and the reaction zone. Yielding occurs at low stress values for elevated temperatures. However, the debonding may require higher stress levels. This temperature effect is investigated, as well as, the response of the evolution of damage versus stress. The theoretical model shows similar behavior as the experimental observations which are shown in Figures 4 and 5. The strain rate effect on the evolution of the damage variable is also studied

Figure 2: Comparison of the Proposed Viscoplasticity Model with Experimental Results [1] at Elevated Temperatures

Figure 3: Comparison of the Viscoplastic Damage Model with Experimental Results [8] of the $(90)_{8s}$ Layup at Elevated Temperature of 538°C

Figure 4: Comparison of the Viscoplastic Damage Model with Experimental Results [8,] of the 90_(8s) Layup at different Elevated Temperatures of 538°C and 649°C

Figure 5: Temperature Effect on the Damage Variable ϕ for (90)_{8s} Layup

here. As indicated by Ju [6], higher strain rates cause retardation of the growth of damage in the materials. This characteristic behavior of the material is also validated by the proposed theory. For this reason different strain rates are used and the corresponding damage evolution curves are generated. As expected with the strain rate increase less damage occurs due to the hardening and consequently less damage is obtained at the same stress level. This is shown for both phases, matrix and fiber in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Strain Rate Effect on the Damage Variable ϕ of the $(90)_{8s}$ Layup

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